

SOME COMMENTS ON MODERN COMMUNICATIVE ASPECTS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the modern communicative aspects of learning foreign languages. In it, the interest and need to learn English as a foreign language, especially in the era of modern development, is increasing. The article provides information on several new approaches and methods as today's communicative aspects of English language learning, based on analyzes and examples.

Introduction. The study of a foreign language both in the recent past and in our time poses a number of tasks for teachers. The main objective of the study is to consider the three main components of language communication. The article formulates the premises that actualize the issue of the auxiliary function of descriptive grammar. Particular attention is paid to the division of signs into ready-made and new. The study emphasizes the purely auxiliary function of descriptive grammar, which can never and under no circumstances become the main tool for mastering the sign-forming means of language, that is, studying a foreign language.

When studying a foreign language, the possibilities of practical communication, and the need for it, are usually immeasurably less. But then there appears an opportunity for rational organization of the sign material being mastered, in which it is pre-arranged according to productive structural models and supplied with special intensive exercises to activate each of them separately. The difference between mastering one's native and foreign languages is not at all that (as some naively believe) in the first case "one can do without studying grammar", and in the second case "one absolutely cannot". In both cases, one must equally master grammatical sign-forming means (if the goal is to master production) and in both cases this cannot be achieved by memorizing "grammar rules".

Results and discussion. The difference is that in the sphere of the native language the process of mastering sign-forming means proceeds mainly spontaneously, while in the sphere of a foreign language it must be consciously guided and directed by the author of the textbook and the teacher, who must already "know the grammar" down to the finer points in order to be able to correctly arrange and introduce into communication practice the sign-forming means to be activated. However, the role of descriptive grammar in mastering the native and foreign languages is not the same. In the sphere of the native language, we become familiar

with grammar after all the main sign-forming means of the spoken language have been mastered by us spontaneously and purely practically.

The role of grammar here is reduced mainly to “correcting” the existing dialectical and other deviations from the accepted language norm, as well as introducing us to the area of specific structures and signs of writing. It is here, in the sphere of written literary language, that the main activity of traditional grammar unfolds; it only comes into being with the introduction of writing, when the need arises to eliminate secondary sign variants and develop a single language norm. That is why traditional grammar is interested primarily in those structures that are typical for written, but not for spoken communication. In the sphere of a foreign language, which is usually studied at a conscious age, the role of descriptive grammar is somewhat different. When mastering many sign-forming means of a foreign language (not only written, but also spoken), their description may be useful; as a result of mastering a group of structures, it is sometimes advisable to give a descriptive summary of what has been mastered.

Structures that are fundamentally different from the structures of the native language deserve special attention. But all this only emphasizes the purely auxiliary function of descriptive grammar, which can never and under no circumstances become the main tool for mastering the sign-forming means of language.

The main goal of training is the formation of communicative competence of students. The meaning of this term will be clearer and more understandable in comparison with the concept of grammatical competence. Grammatical competence is the ability to correctly construct phrases and sentences, correctly use and coordinate tenses, this is knowledge of parts of speech and knowledge of how sentences of different types are structured.

Grammatical competence, as a rule, is the center of attention of many textbooks, which provide certain grammatical rules and exercises for practicing and reinforcing these rules. Undoubtedly, grammatical competence is an important, but far from the only aspect in language teaching. Usage is a much more important and complex aspect, which the communicative approach focuses on. A person who has fully mastered all the grammar rules and is able to construct sentences correctly may find difficulties in real communication in a foreign language, in real communication. That is, the person will experience a lack of communicative competence. It should be taken into account that the communicative method of preparing students is already used to prepare for testing in the formats of international British exams in English.

Communicative competence may include the following aspects:

- knowledge of usage, i.e. how, by whom and when language is used for various purposes and functions,
- knowledge of how language changes depending on a particular communicative situation and the participants in this situation (for example, knowledge of the differences between formal and informal speech, oral and written).
- the ability to create, read and understand texts of various types and natures (for example, stories, interviews, dialogues, reports).
- the ability to maintain a conversation even with a limited vocabulary and grammar base.

One of the main differences of the method is the use of induction, not deduction. That is, there is no need for the teacher to lecture and formulate rules: they are comprehended by the student themselves, even without their verbal formulation. Previously, teaching foreign languages was mainly aimed at developing grammatical competence. It was believed that grammar exercises that do not take into account the context help to develop the habit of using the language correctly. By memorizing dialogues and phrases, correcting errors in oral or written form, and constant monitoring by the teacher, old methods unsuccessfully attempted to avoid incorrect speech.

However, the communicative approach focuses primarily not on the correctness of language structures (although this aspect also remains important), but on other parameters:

- interaction of participants in the communication process, that is, awareness of possible options for the development of dialogues,
- clarification and achievement of a common communicative goal,
- attempts to explain and express things in different ways, that is, development of the skill of paraphrasing,
- expansion of the competence of one participant in communication due to communication with other participants.

When using the communicative approach, the teacher does not lecture or formulate rules using grammatical terms, but, as a rule, acts as:

- assistant,
- friend,
- advisor.

The main focus is on group learning. The task of the teacher and students is to learn to work together, to move away from individualized learning. The student learns to listen to his comrades, conduct conversations and discussions in a group, work on projects together with other group members. The student is more oriented towards his/her group mates than towards his/her teacher as a model. An effective method is also to involve the student in a professional language environment simultaneously with studying in a communicative language group.

All the above components of language proficiency are mastered through exercises in language communication - more or less spontaneous, but almost continuous in the case of the native language and much less prolonged, but differentiated and purposeful in the rational mastering of a foreign language. The acquisition of some information about the language plays only an auxiliary and subordinate role in the process of mastering the language, being not vitally necessary, but in a number of particular cases a desirable accompanying component of this process. With reasonable and very moderate dosing, the description of some linguistic phenomena can accelerate their mastery, but only on condition that this does not violate the main content of language teaching - organized practical exercises in communicative activity. It should not be forgotten that the rational setting of teaching a foreign language requires the most profound preliminary study (including statistical) of all aspects of a given language, considered as a sum of facts.

Only painstaking scientific research work by a philologist to compile the most objective, complete and comprehensive description of language possible (the first approach to

language) can create the necessary conditions for the effective acquisition of language as a means of communication (the second approach to language), but not for the purpose of communicating all this information to the student (which can only lead to a complete failure of learning), but for the correct selection, organization and presentation of the language material to be acquired.

Conclusion. Based on what has been said, we can formulate the content of "language proficiency" or "language knowledge" as follows. Knowing a language means being able to participate fully in the linguistic communication of a given language community or part of it. To do this, it is necessary to store in memory a certain set of images of linguistic signs of all orders, have sign-formation skills, that is, be able to correctly (in accordance with the norms existing in the language community) form new signs (syntagmas, sentences, messages) from signs stored in memory, according to productive structural models (grammatical structures and semi-finished signs). In addition, to have communication techniques, that is, the skills of physically reproducing signs at the transmitting end and receiving (understanding) them at the receiving end of the communication line at the accepted tempo of communication.

Accordingly, the process of mastering a language (native or foreign) cannot but be reduced in its main features to the following: imprinting in memory the necessary set of ready-made signs of all orders, mastering the technique of sign formation at the level of syntagmas, sentences and messages, acquiring the skills of physically reproducing signs and understanding them.

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